

USE OF STRONG AND POWERFUL CONCRETE IN MODERN CONSTRUCTION

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Annotation. The article discusses the possibilities of using modern high-strength concrete in the construction of high-rise buildings in world practice. The advantages and disadvantages of high-strength concrete in the construction of buildings are analyzed. The prospects for using high-strength concrete in the construction industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan are determined.

Key words: High-rise buildings, world practice, high-strength concrete, homogeneity of the concrete mixture, compressive strength of concrete.

Introduction. The construction of high-rise buildings, engineering structures, bridges, fir trees and other structures requires the use of effective building materials that must meet certain technical and economic requirements [1, 3]. This material is high-strength concrete. High mechanical strength, corrosion resistance and resistance to aggressive environments, gas and water resistance put high-strength concrete beyond competition compared to traditional concrete [2, 6].

Modern construction is characterized by an increase in the number of storeys of buildings, while the loads on load-bearing structures increase.

Now in European countries, high-strength concrete includes concrete mixtures with a compressive strength from 60 to 130 MPa. Such concretes are produced strictly according to the developed norms and rules given in the regulatory documents of various advanced countries. By using a binder grain size of up to 600 microns and reducing the water-cement ratio to 0.15, concrete strength of up to 200 MPa is achieved. In this case, they talk about super-strong concrete [8, 9].

The expression “high-strength concrete” was first used in 1929 in the USA, where new concretes and their components were studied for the construction of high-rise buildings, the compressive strength of which reached 130 MPa. In Europe, namely in Germany, the first high-strength concrete was produced in the 40s of the last century. In 1966, concrete with a compressive strength of 140 MPa was obtained in laboratory conditions, and in 1988, tubings from class B85 concrete were produced under industrial conditions [4, 7].

The first high-strength concretes were produced using rigid mixtures, using specific compaction methods and autoclave curing [10, 11, 12]. It was found that the weakest component in concrete is cement stone. Strength in this case depends proportionally on the water-cement ratio. Therefore, lowering it was the first task for the designers. The use of modern plasticizers can significantly increase the strength characteristics of concrete [13, 14].

Experimental studies have shown that using high-strength concrete for load-bearing elements of frame-type buildings ensures good seismic stability of structures. The cross-sectional dimensions of structural elements made of high-strength concrete are smaller, which leads to a reduction in dead weight and improved economic efficiency of construction. The high strength of concrete is also effective for prestressed structures. This ensures the use of strong reinforcing bars and ropes, which significantly increases the rigidity of the elements and their crack resistance. Due to this, prestressed reinforced concrete structures are used in large-span and large-scale structures. The use of high-strength, high-density concrete is effective for structures subject to cyclic and blast loads.

Among the main features of high-strength concrete are waterproofness and corrosion resistance, which ensures the reliability and durability of reinforced concrete structures.

High-strength concrete has the following advantages:

- the use of standardized formwork for the manufacture of columns in factory production conditions, for various loads, the possibility of manufacturing columns

for all floors, which makes it possible to use high-strength concrete on the lower floors in monolithic construction;

- when working in bending, there is a decrease in the working height of the section or an increase in the load-bearing capacity of structures;
- reducing the consumption of concrete and reinforcement and, accordingly, saving costs for transportation and installation of structures;
- earlier stripping and preliminary compression;
- the time for gaining initial strength is accelerated, allowing you to start using the element earlier;
- high density, water and gas impermeability due to the low content of capillary pores;
- the ability to create different sections of elements when increasing the span of structures working on bending;
- increased wear resistance;
- reduction in the cross-sectional dimensions of the elements, which leads to a reduction in the cost of formwork;
- resistance to aggressive environments due to high density.

However, despite the undeniable advantages of high-strength concrete, one should also remember its disadvantages:

- the nature of the destruction of elements made of high-strength concrete is brittle due to its high strength and rigidity, therefore special measures are required when designing and constructing structures made from it to ensure reliable operation of buildings;
- self-compacting and cast concrete mixtures, as a rule, have high shrinkage, the value of which can reach up to 0.8...1.0 mm/m.

For the manufacture and production of high-strength concrete, the industry must use high-quality materials, namely:

- finely ground components;
- inert fillers of the required fractions and purity;

- highly active and stable cement;
- modern plasticizing additives.

Conclusions. There are very few examples of the use of high-strength concrete in the Republic of Uzbekistan, so this issue is relevant. Based on global experience in the use of high-strength concrete, it is necessary to develop structures based on this concrete and improve calculation and design methods.

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